

NAVIGATING RESETTLEMENT: AFGHAN STUDENTS'
INTEGRATION IN THE UNITED STATES POST-2021

by

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ABSTRACT

This study delves into the lived experiences of Afghan students resettled in the United States post-2021, particularly those attending Bard College, offering insights into their challenges, support needs, and integration into the new environment. Bard College, renowned for its commitment to inclusivity and social justice, provided full scholarships to 75 Afghan students, exemplifying its dedication to aiding displaced individuals.

Findings reveal a number of obstacles encountered by the newly arrived Afghan students, ranging from linguistic and academic disparities to socio-cultural adjustments and emotional stressors. Notably, the study emphasizes the importance of tailored support mechanisms, such as cultural sensitivity training, mentorship initiatives, and customized academic resources, in facilitating successful integration at institutions like Bard College. By shedding light on the experiences of Afghan students at Bard College, this research contributes to the broader discourse on refugee education and integration. It seeks to inform institutional practices, policy frameworks, and community initiatives aimed at creating more inclusive and supportive environments for displaced individuals worldwide.

This study offers practical insights to better assist displaced Afghan students in their academic journey at Bard College and beyond, while advancing global discussions on refugee education and integration.

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Introduction

In 2021, Afghanistan saw the withdrawal of US troops and the abrupt takeover of Kabul by the Taliban in August. After two decades of war and a massive \$2.3 trillion spent on the conflict, the United States concluded its presence in Afghanistan, marking the return of the Taliban to power. (Boni, F. (2021).

Afghanistan has faced instability for over four decades. In August 2021, there was widespread news about the Biden administration's decision to pull out US troops from Afghanistan. This surprised many, especially in the US, as the Taliban quickly regained control of the capital, Kabul. This change in power prompted a large-scale evacuation effort, bringing Afghan citizens to the United States, with connections to the previous leadership or having worked with the US government including students. Since August 2021, over 76,000 Afghans have arrived in the US, and more are still coming (Razzaque, A. (2023).

The year 2021, brought challenges and opportunities for Afghan students resettling in the U.S., shaping their experiences in a distinctive manner. Understanding the context of this post-2021 resettlement is essential for exploring the integration dynamics and educational experiences of Afghan students and by understanding the historical and geopolitical backdrop against which this resettlement occurred, we can gain valuable insights into the broader implications for refugee resettlement and higher education in the United States.

Since August 2021, Afghan women's lives have undergone a drastic transformation. Legal and constitutional rights, as well as two decades of progress, were erased swiftly by the Taliban.

Their governance-imposed restrictions on women's public participation, reinforcing gender apartheid through numerous decrees in education, employment, and public spaces (Barr, 2021). Girls aged 12 and older no longer receive education. Secondary schools for girls have been closed for a year, making Afghanistan the sole country where girls are legally denied secondary education. Achieving UN Sustainable Development Goal 4 for inclusive education is unlikely. Despite optimism for school reopening, girls were turned away on the first day of the new school year in March 2022. (Glinski and Kumar, 2022). According to Women, Peace and Security (WPS) Index, which evaluates, and positions 177 nations based on their levels of women's inclusion, justice, and security. Afghanistan holds the lowest position among 177 countries concerning the condition of women.

Colleges and universities in the United State have increased efforts to provide housing and financial aid for numerous Afghan refugees arriving in the United States after the swift departure of American military forces from Afghanistan and the subsequent assumption of power by the Taliban. Goddard and Bard Colleges offer housing for Afghan refugees, while Goodwin University, the University of Bridgeport, and Northern Virginia Community College provide housing and support. UC Berkeley and San Jose State University raised funds for Afghan refugee assistance (Dennon, 2021).

Bard College, known for its commitment to inclusivity and social justice, emerged as a haven for many of these displaced individuals, offering them an opportunity to continue their education and rebuild their lives. Bard awarded full scholarships to 75 Afghan students, covering

tuition, accommodation, and meals. Most Afghan students plan to stay in the U.S. for asylum, while others hope to return home (Bard College, n.d.).

Research question

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. How are male/female students evacuated from Afghanistan and studying at Bard College experiencing the resettlement process in the U.S?
2. What are the key challenges they face?
3. What critical support systems are necessary for their successful integration into the new environment?

Significance of the Study

This research aimed to delve into the lived experiences of Afghan displaced students, shedding light on the various challenges, hardships, and obstacles they navigate during their resettlement and academic pursuits in the United States post-2021. This study is crucial for both academic research and practical applications. Understanding how newly arrived displaced Afghan students adjust to life in the United States, particularly at Bard College, holds significant importance. This research not only provides insights into general student integration but also offers specific understanding of the challenges they face and the support they require. The aim of this study is to offer practical guidance to better assist these displaced students in their journey towards success at Bard College and beyond.

By understanding the unique experiences of these students, we can pinpoint specific areas where they might benefit from focused support, such as cultural sensitivity training, mentorship

initiatives, and customized academic resources. This doesn't just enhance the students' experience, but also fosters a more inclusive and productive educational setting for all.

Furthermore, the insights gleaned from this study extend beyond the specific circumstances, providing valuable guidance for institutions, policymakers, and communities grappling with similar challenges in assisting displaced populations. By illuminating the experiences of Afghan students at Bard College, this research endeavors to make a substantive contribution to the global dialogue on refugee education and integration. In doing so, it aspires to create environments that are more inclusive and supportive for displaced individuals on a global scale.

Research Ethics

As a researcher, I prioritized participant confidentiality and data security in accordance with the New York University's Institutional Review Board (IRB) protocol. Qualitative data potentially identifying subjects was anonymized by replacing specific details with pseudonyms. Participants will be approached through collaboration with Bard College and prior to interviews, participants were informed about the purpose and significance of the research, ensuring they understood before agreeing to participate. Additionally, participants were required to give their consent before the interview, which was documented through signed agreement, aligning with ethical considerations of my thesis.

Prior to initiating this study, participants were informed about the purpose and significance of the research, ensuring they understood before agreeing to participate. I also addressed any questions

they had about my research throughout the process. Additionally, participants were provided with a consent form before the interview, assuring them of the research's safety and ethical standards.

Literature Review

This section will review the relevant literature related to the core themes of the thesis. It will start with the historical context of Afghanistan, covering key events such as the Soviet-Afghan war, the rise of the Taliban, the US invasion, and the evacuation process post-2021. Furthermore, it will provide contextual background on the education landscape of Afghanistan, highlighting numerous challenges. Subsequently, it will explore the resettlement of Afghan immigrants in the US, focusing on the experiences of international students and their adjustments in the United States compared to their home countries.

Afghanistan's Historical Context

Afghanistan, enduring internal conflicts for decades, experiences significant migration due to economic hardship. This continuous migration trend spans approximately 50 years. It stems from various factors such as climate change-induced disasters, conflicts, security concerns and economic instability. Migration opportunities are unequal based on economic and social status, favoring urban and educated groups for migration to industrialized nations. Economic opportunities and demographic pressures, particularly among the youth, further contribute to migration. Additionally, migration exacerbates vulnerability, particularly for women (Dashti, 2022).

Soviet-Afghan War

The largest migration event in Afghanistan's history unfolded during the Soviet Union's invasion from 1979 to 1989, more than 5 million Afghans were forced to migrate to neighboring countries such as Iran, Pakistan, and Turkey. This mass exodus led to two million Afghans internally displaced and represented about one-fifth of Afghanistan's entire population at that time. After the Soviet withdrawal in 1989, internal conflicts over power-sharing led to further migration as Afghans sought safety and stability (Dashti, 2021 as cited in Dashti, 2022).

The Soviet-Afghan War stands as a pivotal moment in Afghan history, significantly contributing to the emergence of the Afghan diaspora. Fought between Soviet communists and Afghan insurgents known as the Mujahideen during the Cold War, the conflict commenced in 1979 and concluded in 1988. However, the enduring repercussions of Soviet and U.S. involvement in Afghanistan paved the way for the rise of the Taliban regime and subsequent ongoing conflicts. Resulting in widespread devastation of infrastructure, the war left Afghanistan among the most impoverished nations globally (Mohamed, 2023). Significant literacy programs were initiated for both genders, alongside reforms such as the abolition of bride price. Despite opposition from rural leaders, women gained improved access to education and opportunities to participate as university faculty during this period (PBS, 2006).

Rise of Taliban

The Taliban, characterized by Islamic fundamentalism, governed Afghanistan from 1996 to 2001, until a U.S.-led intervention overthrew them for harboring al-Qaeda and Osama bin Laden. Originating in the early 1990s, the Taliban emerged from a faction of Afghan mujahideen who resisted the Soviet occupation, supported covertly by the U.S. Central Intelligence Agency

and the Pakistani Inter-Services Intelligence directorate (ISI). Their ranks included young Pashtun tribesmen educated in Pakistani madrassas, or seminaries, hence the name "Taliban," meaning "students" in Pashto. Pashtuns constitute the largest ethnic group in Afghanistan, particularly in the southern and eastern regions. Following their downfall, the Taliban regrouped in Pakistan under the leadership of Mullah Mohammed Omar, leading an insurgency against the Western-backed government in Kabul. (Laub, 2014).

In his book 'Afghanistan: The Soviet War,' American journalist and author Ed Girardet argues that Afghanistan's issues gained prominence following the emergence of the Taliban, suggesting shared responsibility between the Soviets and the US for their rise. Girardet notes that the Taliban, originally Mujahideen fighters during the Soviet-Afghan War, originated from Eastern/Southern Afghanistan. While the Soviet Union sought to maintain Communist control despite popular resistance, the US aided Afghan rebels in overthrowing the Communist regime and countering the spread of Communism. To weaken Soviet influence, the Central Intelligence Agency provided financial and military support to local leaders and Mujahideen rebels (Girardet, 1986, pp. 175 as referenced in Mohamed, 2023).

In October 2001, the United States and its allies launched a military intervention in the country, swiftly removing the Taliban government after it refused to surrender terrorist leader Osama bin Laden in the aftermath of the 9/11 attacks carried out by al-Qaeda (Council on Foreign Relations, 2023). This intervention prompted over 300,000 Afghans to leave the country in 2001. In contrast, between 2002 and 2008, the Afghan government's Voluntary Return Program facilitated the repatriation of 4.3 million Afghan immigrants, mainly from Pakistan and Iran,

representing the largest refugee return movement in UNHCR's history. However, the resurgence of the Taliban in 2005, coupled with security challenges, impeded further repatriations (Verduijn, 2020; Lucia, 2015 as cited in Dashti, 2022).

After the 2001 U.S.-led invasion that removed them from power, the Taliban regrouped in Pakistan and steadily regained control of territory. By August 2021, they had once again established authority, aligning with the withdrawal of U.S. troops under a 2020 peace agreement. Despite assurances to safeguard the rights of women and religious and ethnic minorities, the Taliban have enforced a rigid interpretation of Islamic law. Transitioning from an insurgency to a governing entity, they grapple with issues such as ensuring sufficient food supplies and economic prospects for Afghan citizens (Maizland, 2023).

Under Taliban rule, education deteriorated significantly, particularly for girls. The Taliban prioritized religious studies for boys, while nearly all girls were denied access to schooling. Only a small fraction, approximately 3%, of girls received any form of primary education during this period. The ban on female education, along with cultural norms mandating female healthcare providers for women, led to a situation where a vulnerable population received care from inadequately trained providers. (PBS, 2006).

Evacuation Post-2021

In August 2021, the rapid Taliban takeover of Afghanistan drew global attention as Afghans faced the new regime's threats. Western governments had to swiftly organize large-scale evacuation operations, reminiscent of those during World War II, as civilians fled to airports

seeking refuge. Beyond military efforts, various groups like parliamentary representatives, NGOs, and academics actively engaged in saving at-risk Afghans, reflecting widespread concern and grassroots rescue efforts amidst the crisis (Footitt, 2023).

The NATO evacuation from Afghanistan in August 2021 was marked by chaos and desperation as Afghans sought to escape the Taliban takeover. Initially, the evacuation focused on airlifting NATO nationals, but when the Taliban reached Kabul on August 15th, the airport was inundated with Afghans clamoring to flee. The situation quickly spiraled into a scene of pandemonium, with thousands attempting to board planes by any means necessary, resulting in tragic images of people falling from plane wings. Amidst negotiations with the Taliban, American forces cleared the runways by force, allowing evacuation operations to formally commence on August 17th. Overwhelmed by crowds, conditions at the airport were dire, with reports of deaths from heat and hunger, overcrowding, and even people standing in sewage-filled canals just to survive (Film, 2022 as cited in Footitt, 2023).

Afghan Evacuation Figure Post-2021

According to the U.S. Department of State (2021), more than 123,000 people have been safely flown out of Afghanistan. The US airlifted Afghan nationals to US territory, military facilities abroad, and third countries, requiring approval before flying to bases in Qatar, Bahrain, Italy, Spain, Germany, Kuwait, or the United Arab Emirates (De Jong and Sarantidis, 2022). Obtaining precise figures for the August 2021 evacuations is challenging, yet De Jong and Sarantidis (2022) found that Australia, Canada, Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands, the UK, and the US collectively evacuated a significant number of Afghan civilians, including

interpreters, embassy staff, and vulnerable individuals. Australia evacuated 2,984 Afghan nationals with approved visas and a total of 4,168 individuals, while Canada evacuated 2,000 Afghans. Denmark evacuated 1,077, France evacuated 2,600, and Germany evacuated 3,849. The Netherlands evacuated a total of 1,072 individuals, the UK nearly 5,000 Afghans, and the US over 82,015 (76,000 on top check with professor which number to use) Afghans. However, the exact number of former staff members at risk remains unclear.

Most Afghan evacuees arriving in the US were granted Humanitarian Parole, a temporary entry status granted for one to two years for humanitarian reasons. This status was given due to their lack of other legal statuses, such as completed SIV, permanent residency, or citizenship (De Jong and Sarantidis, 2022).

Decades of conflict in Afghanistan have deeply affected vulnerable groups, especially children and women. The resulting instability has led to mass displacement, with Afghan evacuees arriving in the United States under different legal statuses and experience varying integration trajectories, with Afghan evacuees facing challenges in resettlement programs and job market integration. Despite refugees' easier economic integration, Special Immigrant Visa (SIV) holders fare better in legal integration. Humanitarian Parolees, however, face the most disadvantages due to migration policies and limited rights ((Mohamed, 2023, p. 78).

Integration of Afghan Immigrants in the US Since 1920

Refugees and asylees, although both legally entering the US, have a key difference. Refugees apply from outside the US, showing past or present persecution in their home country,

while asylees apply within the US due to fear of persecution (USCIS, 2024). The concept of refugee status, defined in the 1967 Protocol amending the United Nations 1951 Convention, stipulates that asylum status is only awarded after refugees have entered the US and can provide compelling evidence to a court that returning to their home country would result in persecution or even death (Monger & Yankay, 2013, as cited in Trauth & Harris).

In 1920, a group of 200 Pushtuns migrated to the United States from what was then British India, now part of Pakistan, with some likely being Afghan citizens (Champagne, 1980). Immigration from Afghanistan during the 1930s and 1940s was minimal, consisting mainly of individuals or small family units, primarily from the Afghan elite professions like diplomacy, medicine, engineering, and business, some with European spouses. These early immigrants settled mainly on the East and West coasts and around Washington, D.C.

Between 1953 and 1963, only 78 Afghan individuals acquired American citizenship, but this number increased to 155 in the subsequent decade, reflecting increased travel opportunities and Western educational ties. During this time, Afghan men primarily came to the US for higher education, often staying and later bringing their families. Though some Afghan women also pursued higher education in the US during the late 1950s and 1960s, fewer remained compared to men (Champagne, 1980).

The period from 1973 to 1977 witnessed a notable rise in the naturalization of Afghans, possibly due to political unrest in Afghanistan. Overall, between 1953 and 1977, 343 Afghans became American citizens. Additionally, since 1953, several thousand Afghans obtained resident

alien status, settling in various states across the US. Major Afghan communities are found in cities like Los Angeles, Washington, D.C., and New York, attracted by employment opportunities in these metropolitan areas. The rise of a Marxist regime in Afghanistan in 1978 led to turmoil, prompting many Afghans to immigrate to the United States. This resulted in a notable increase in Afghans seeking student visa extensions and resident alien status. The majority of Afghan Americans maintain strong connections with their extended families back in Afghanistan, despite living in nuclear family setups in the United States. While adapting to their new home, they remain rooted in their Islamic faith, adhering to its principles (Champagne, 1980).

Large numbers of Afghan refugees arrived in the United States following the 1980 Soviet invasion, with statuses including refugee designation, political asylum, family reunification, or illegal entry. Annual arrivals averaged 2,000 to 4,000 until 1989, totaling 45,000 to 75,000 refugees. Post-1989, most Afghan immigrants entered through family reunification, leading to clustered settlements and a shift from educated professionals to less educated immigrants with limited English proficiency. Challenges in integration included language barriers, depleted resources, and lack of social support. Afghan Americans prioritize economic stability, cultural preservation, and community cohesion over traditional integration metrics, often after seeking refuge in countries like Pakistan or Iran before coming to the United States (Elgo, 2017).

Education

For over a thousand years, education has been prevalent in Afghanistan and numerous other Muslim nations. Islamic education, though facing challenges from prevailing beliefs and superstitions, has historically reached a broad spectrum of the population early on. It's worth noting

that Islamic schools frequently incorporated subjects commonly categorized as 'secular,' including mathematics, literacy, literature, and occasionally vocational training (Karlsson & Mansory, 2008).

Islamic education is pervasive throughout Afghanistan, reaching nearly the entire population, including rural areas. While Quranic teaching is central, basic literacy and numeracy are also taught, even in rural settings. Afghanistan's educational system comprises traditional, modern, and Islamic education. In some regions, Islamic practices intertwine with pre-Islamic customs, occasionally conflicting with Quranic teachings, such as practices of revenge. Islamic education has roots dating back to the arrival of Islam, with religious instruction commonly provided by knowledgeable individuals in mosques. The depth of religious knowledge varies based on location and community size (Esmaily et al., 2010).

Following the Taliban's takeover of Kabul in 1996, girls' education was halted by Mullah Omar, citing security concerns, a policy that persisted until 2001. While the Taliban displayed hostility towards Ministry of Education schools after re-emerging in 2004-05, formal opposition to education diminished by 2009, and direct attacks on schools decreased until 2015. Taliban policies on education remained inconsistent, with sporadic attacks still occurring, although they have released statements supporting education and reports suggest improved delivery in Taliban-influenced areas since 2011. However, education quality remains poor, especially for girls, and school closures are sometimes used for control or leverage. Local Taliban support education if they have influence over curriculum and funding, often negotiated through settlements mediated

by elders and religious leaders, alongside unofficial talks with the Ministry of Education (Rubin and Rudeforth, 2016).

The extended conflict in Afghanistan has hampered higher education development, with approximately six million Afghans, including qualified higher education personnel, leaving the country during the civil war. This significant emigration depleted Afghanistan's skilled workforce, thereby impeding progress in higher education (Samady, 2001, as cited in Sabri, 2019).

According to PBS (2006), the report "Flying Down to Kabul: Women in Afghanistan: Education" that decades of conflict have ravaged Afghanistan's education infrastructure, but since 2001, there had been a notable increase in educational engagement. By 2005, the country witnessed a substantial rise in enrollment, with over 5.2 million students, including approximately 1.82-1.95 million girls and women, actively participating in formal education. Furthermore, there was a significant enrollment in vocational and non-formal education programs, signifying a remarkable improvement from the oppressive regime of the Taliban.

Taliban's recent discriminatory educational policies in Afghanistan are adversely affecting both genders, as evidenced by the departure of skilled educators and the implementation of regressive curriculum alterations. These shifts have instilled heightened apprehensions surrounding school attendance, resulting in declining enrollment rates and a pervasive sense of hopelessness about the future. Consequently, the Taliban's actions pose the risk of generating a lost generation. These actions in Afghanistan have also led to the removal of female teachers from boys' schools, resulting in unqualified or absent instructors. They've also intensified the use of

corporal punishment for minor infractions, including public beatings. Furthermore, the Taliban's removal of subjects like arts, sports, English, and civic education has lowered the quality of education. (Human Rights Watch, 2023).

Afghanistan's education system has plunged into crisis since August 2021. While the media has focused on the Taliban's ban on girls' and women's secondary and higher education, the violations extend beyond gender restrictions. Boys across various provinces face new obstacles, including the absence of female teachers, heightened corporal punishment, decreased attendance, removal of key subjects, declining educational standards, increased school-related anxiety, and loss of hope. Such actions by the Taliban contradict international human rights norms and educational standards.

A report by Fetrat (2023) documents Taliban's policies and practices since their resurgence in August 2021, Afghanistan's education system has plunged into crisis. While the media has focused on the Taliban's ban on girls' and women's secondary and higher education, the violations extend beyond gender restrictions. Boys across various provinces face new obstacles, including the absence of female teachers, heightened corporal punishment, decreased attendance, removal of key subjects, declining educational standards, increased school-related anxiety, and loss of hope. Such actions by the Taliban contradict international human rights norms and educational standards.

Education centers and NGO-supported institutes in Afghanistan's southern regions have been closed by the Taliban until further notice. These centers primarily catered to girls, who face

restrictions on education beyond the sixth grade (Associated Press, 2023). Afghanistan has struggled with low literacy rates, particularly among women, with only 20.6% reported as literate, one of the lowest figures globally. Education and literacy serve as catalysts for transforming women's lives, granting them the power to drive positive change in economic development, healthcare, and societal advancement (UNESCO, n.d.)

According to Trako and Molina (2019), in low-income countries like Afghanistan, education is hindered by weak state control and under-resourced local institutions. This creates a cycle where inadequately trained educators struggle to teach subsequent generations, with improving student learning not prioritized.

Afghanistan, under the Taliban regime, stands as the sole location globally where the education of girls is prohibited (Gonnella-Platts, 2022). According to the information provided in the Afghanistan Humanitarian Response Plan 2024 (n.d.) and the WOOA 2023 report, the primary obstacle preventing children, especially girls, from attending school is the current bans on education. A significant 55% of respondents identified these new bans as the main barrier keeping girls out of school. Furthermore, the number of secondary school girls unable to attend continues to increase. An additional 297,152 girls who were in 6th grade in 2023 will be deprived of education in the 2023/2024 academic year.

The reconstruction of a nation across various sectors hinges on its education system, with higher education serving as the cornerstone of economic, social, and cultural development (Esmaeily et al., 2010).

Experiences of International Students in the United States

The United States continues to be the preferred destination for students pursuing higher education overseas. In the 2022-23 academic year, the number of international students enrolled at U.S. colleges and universities surged by 12%, reaching a total of 1,057,188. This significant increase, the highest growth rate in over four decades, nearly restored international enrollment to pre-pandemic levels. According to the recent Open Doors report by the Institute of International Education (IIE), international students now constitute 5.6% of the total college student population in the United States. According to the National Association of Foreign Student Advisers (NAFSA), international students studying in U.S. colleges and universities contribute \$40.1 billion to the economy and support 368,333 jobs across various sectors (NAFSA, 2023).

According to Morinaka (2007), the primary motivation for international students to pursue education, teaching, and research opportunities in the United States stems from the global acknowledgment of the exceptional quality and esteemed reputation of American higher education and its numerous institutions. After completing their studies, many international students choose to work in the U.S. These individuals, who stay after graduation, make significant contributions to American society, benefiting the nation. (as cited in Ejiofo, 2010).

While studying in the US offers valuable hands-on learning experiences not commonly found in students' home countries, the decision to pursue education there entails various challenges before, during, and after the journey. International students encounter both rewards and difficulties. On one hand, they benefit from exposure to new cultures, societies, and career

prospects. On the other hand, they grapple with academic, social, and cultural hurdles. (Hegarty, 2014, as cited in Sabri, 2019).

Cross-Cultural Dynamics in the Learning Processes of International Students

The presence of international students in colleges enriches the collegiate environment by fostering diversity in culture, languages, and educational backgrounds, which can be advantageous for both American students and professors. International students' experiences in the United States may involve their participation in meaningful activities that enhance their learning and personal growth (Glass, Buus, and Braskamp, 2013).

While most students in the study does not face obstacles related to access or exclusion, Almurideef suggests in his research the importance of introducing additional cross-cultural events and activities. This recommendation aims to strengthen the international program and broaden its appeal to a more diverse range of students (Almurideef, 2016).

Active participation in events celebrating diverse cultures, engaging in current affairs discussions, and participating in classroom dialogues can mitigate feelings of threat among international students. Moreover, such engagement reduces reliance on authorities for knowledge and fosters cross-cultural peer relationships (Glass et al., 2013).

Negative emotions such as frustration, anger, and stress stemmed from language and academic disparities, lead to feelings of marginalization and alienation among students in both academic and social settings due to socio-cultural gaps (Xiong & Zhou, 2018).

Based on a model of acculturation focusing on cultural awareness and ethnic loyalty, individuals' level of acculturation is determined by their understanding of both their traditional culture and the host culture. Those more familiar with their own culture than the host culture are less acculturated, while those more familiar with the host culture are well acculturated. Factors influencing acculturation include religious devotion, personal values, age, and power dynamics between minority and majority groups (Padilla & Perez, 2003 as cited in Wahidi, 2015).

Research Design and Methodology

Recognizing my position as an Afghan researcher, I employed a qualitative approach, conducting semi-structured interviews with Afghan students at Bard College who arrived in the US post-2021, ensuring their direct involvement with the research topic. This methodology aimed to deeply explore their resettlement experiences, perspectives, and challenges. Through open-ended questions and guided discussions, the study sought to capture the nuanced narratives of participants, providing valuable qualitative insights into their journey and integration into the new environment. In Spring 2024, I conducted in-depth interviews with six Afghan students (four females, two males) at Bard College, each representing diverse legal statuses within the United States. Interviews were conducted via Zoom and in person on Bard's campus.

Interviews were chosen as the preferred method for delving into participants' lived experiences after the fall of Afghan government in 2021, providing valuable insights to address the research questions effectively. I opted for a smaller sample size to allow for a more comprehensive interview. At the time of the interview, five of these individuals were primarily

located at Bard College, and one in New York City. Participants brought diverse backgrounds, spanning from former employees of the US Embassy in Kabul to individuals working with various organizations in Afghanistan. Five of my participants were former students at the American University of Afghanistan and one was from private University in Kabul, helping them to have proficient command of the English language.

The interviews consisted of twelve questions centered on the challenges students faced, the support systems required for their integration, cultural adjustments, their departure from Afghanistan, and their experiences at Bard College and in the United States. Throughout the interviews, I refrained from interjecting personal viewpoints or ideas. Moreover, I encouraged interviewees to freely discuss any additional topics or thoughts they deemed significant. This methodology ensured a transparent and unbiased approach in collecting information for my thesis.

Positionality

In conducting this research, I was aware of my own positionality and mindful of my own background and personal experiences as an Afghan student who arrived in 2022 after fall of Afghan government and in navigating my own resettlement in the United States. My interactions within the Afghan community and academia, including my time at the American University of Afghanistan and visits to Bard College, facilitated rapport with participants. Several students willingly participated, driven by a desire to aid their fellow Afghans. Given the participants' English proficiency, interviews were conducted without the need for translators, lasting between one to two hours. Aware of my biases, I aimed to understand and highlight the challenges faced by Afghan students in the US, including their experiences of resettlement, evacuation from

Afghanistan, trauma and ongoing educational struggles. My goal is to advocate for the improvement of Afghan students' lives in US colleges and contribute to global discussions on refugee education and integration, ultimately striving for more inclusive and supportive environments for displaced individuals worldwide.

Research site and sample

The study site for this paper was Bard College, situated in New York state, USA. Bard College hosts a community of over 100 Afghan students pursuing their education after the fall of Afghan government in 2021 (Bard College Center for Civic Engagement, 2023). Participants were selected through purposive sampling, targeting graduate and undergraduate Afghan students with unique insights and relevant resettlement experiences post-2021, ensuring alignment with the research focus.

The student participants brought varied resettlement experiences prior to arriving in the US. For instance, one student came from Kyrgyzstan, another spent a year in Iraq before moving to the United States. Similarly, two students were evacuated directly through the US-led evacuation in August 2021, while one spent three months in Iraq before arriving on an F1 visa. Additionally, one student was flown to Uganda through a chartered flight before coming to the US on an F1 visa. By centering on the voices and experiences of the students themselves, this study seeks to offer a comprehensive understanding of their resettlement experiences.

Findings

The findings, drawn from interviews and literature reviews, highlights the integration and resettlement dynamics of Afghan students in the United States post-2021, as well as the challenges they face at Bard College during the same period. I narrowed down a broad topic by focusing on four specific themes from the literature review: Academic Experiences and Challenges, Social and Cultural Dynamics, economic challenges, and psychological struggles faced by Afghan students in the US. Through analysis, I explored connections between these themes and identified new insights, given the limited literature on Afghan students' experiences in the United States.

1. Academic Experiences and Challenges of Afghan Students in the US

The abrupt withdrawal of US forces and the subsequent takeover of Afghanistan by the Taliban in 2021 significantly impacted the educational and academic experiences of the participants in my research. As explained in my literature review, international students find it crucial to integrate with domestic peers in the US. However, language, cultural, and social gaps pose obstacles to effective communication and hinder their ability to connect with American students (Xiong & Zhou, 2018). Upon arrival in the United States, participants faced initial challenges adapting to Bard College's rigorous academic expectations, contrasting with their prior educational experiences in Afghanistan and most common during their communication were the pronouns and genders. One participants said "I struggled with pronouns as it was never taught to us while we were learning English language".

International students prioritize friendship as a significant and enduring bond, contrasting with the more superficial nature of American friendships. Consequently, international students often find it easier to form lasting connections with other international students rather than with Americans due to cultural differences in friendship norms (Johnson et al., 2018 as cited in Sabri, 2019). The evolving perspectives on cultural differences and interpersonal dynamics highlighted the importance of understanding individual differences, both within the academic setting and broader social interactions.

Arab women encounter challenges when adapting to cultures with open and shared gender interactions. This difficulty is also experienced by Afghan female students who, despite attending single-gender schools, confront integration hurdles upon entering coeducational public and private universities (Sabri, 2019). According to my findings, newly arrived students find it surprising and hard to accept the new culture of shared bathrooms and adapting this new culture instantly. “Shared bathroom or bathroom that is for both gender was big thing when I first came to the US” said one participant.

Academic Integration

International students at US colleges and universities contribute significant cultural, educational, and economic diversity to campus communities. The internationalization of campuses fosters cultural awareness, equipping students with valuable skills for a global workforce. However, as international student recruitment rises, universities must address the adjustment challenges they face by offering appropriate support services to ensure their retention (Darwish, 2022).

During the interviews, participants discussed how the whole education environment including syllabus, coursework and teaching methods differs and find it completely opposite to what they have seen back home and find it hard to adjust and adapt. According to Trako and Molina (2019), the primary school education system in Afghanistan faces significant challenges. Fifteen percent of primary school teachers are absent, and those present spend 80 percent of their time on learning activities. However, the short school day of 3 hours and 25 minutes means students receive less effective teaching compared to Sub-Saharan African countries. Only 40 percent of teachers show proficiency in fourth-grade language and math curriculums. Teachers struggle with pedagogical knowledge, including reading comprehension and formulating learning objectives. Few teachers assess student learning or provide feedback. Less than a third of teachers keep records of student performance, and even fewer accurately estimate student performance. Overall, less than 20 percent of teachers implement effective teaching practices. These challenges highlight systemic issues in teacher selection, training, and support, hindering the delivery of high-quality education in Afghanistan.

In Afghanistan's education system, there is little emphasis placed on the development of reading and writing skills. “Western students or Chinese, Indians and Bangladesh, they were better in science and in STEM they were too good and Afghans in general were not good, but it was because we never had good professors in STEM or focused on the program in Afghanistan” said one participant. It shows that the educational system in Afghanistan failed to assist the students in acquiring essential academic skills and knowledge.

Most Afghan students who come to the US for graduate-level studies are typically unfamiliar with research and its significant role in academic work at the graduate level (Esmaeily, Pahwa, Thompson, and Watts, 2010). Extended periods of occupation and civil conflict have led to widespread pessimism and suspicion among the population. This has led to hesitancy in cooperation, even when it would be mutually beneficial. Additionally, many beneficiaries, including some graduate students, hold unrealistic perceptions about certain activities and the partnership as a whole (Esmaeily et al., 2010). Participants' academic challenges among six participants were based on factors like; their English competency, academic experiences in more than one university and familiarity with American education system compared to Afghan education system.

International students tend to participate less in classroom activities compared to their American counterparts, possibly due to their previous experience with rote learning methods in their home countries, which offer limited opportunities for student discussion during class. Students struggle to adapt to a new culture while managing heavy academic reading requirements. Limited language proficiency hindered their progress, making them hesitant to engage with professors and peers. This, coupled with their prior experience with teacher-centered lectures, led to minimal classroom participation, exacerbated by the emphasis on participation in grading (Lyken-Segosebe, 2017). While adapting to life in the United States, participants encountered challenges in communication due to language barriers. People often misinterpreted their messages, highlighting the need to learn effective communication skills later.

Research indicates that international students require support, encouragement, and nurturing as they adapt to college life in the United States. Crucial to their acclimation is the collaborative effort between academic and student services departments (Hegarty, 2014 as cited in Darwish, 2022). A frequently encountered theme concerning academic challenges in my interviews was lack of encouragement. Participants stated how talented and hardworking the newly arrived Afghan students are but they lack confidence and belief and encouragement from the Bard college that can help spark students potential at its highest.

Insufficient academic support lead to adverse emotions including stress, a sense of aimlessness, and frustration. Additionally, financial strain emerged as a notable obstacle affecting the mental well-being of East Asian graduate students (Xiong & Zhou, 2018).

2. Social and Cultural Dynamics

Afghan students in the US, like their international counterparts, confront challenges worsened by conflict, displacement, trauma, and the sudden government collapse in 2021, prompting their unexpected departure from Afghanistan. Immigrants often face social rejection and discrimination due to their ethnicity and minority status, distinguished by attire, race, religion, language, and ethnicity. Some adopt aspects of the dominant culture to avoid discrimination, especially when political, economic, or social incentives are involved (Padilla & Perez, 2003 as cited in Wahidi, 2015). For many participants, the most prevalent challenge was communication, particularly regarding the unfamiliarity with pronouns and the issue of misgendering individuals as they were never taught in their English language courses.

The transition from Afghanistan to the United States with its unique culture and lifestyle left an impact on the majority of my participants, leading to feelings of cultural perplexity and emerged as a notable discovery in my research. For instance, participants had no prior involvement or knowledge about the LGBTQ community. It was a new concept to participants, and lacked sufficient information about it and only heard about it through social media.

Students from individualistic cultures may integrate more easily into U.S. mainstream culture, while those from collectivist backgrounds may feel isolated. Unlike their American peers, international students lack familiar support systems to cope with stressors like social isolation and academic pressure. Therefore, universities and educators must address the specific needs and barriers international students face in achieving academic and personal success in the U.S. Counselor education programs, known for their adaptability to diverse student populations, should prioritize understanding and supporting the growing number of international students (Swagler & Ellis, 2003 as cited in Reid & Dixon, 2012). Two out of the six participants found it relatively easy to socialize and integrate upon arriving in the US. This was largely attributed to their previous experiences living outside of Afghanistan after fall of Afghan government in 2021, in places such as Iraq and Bishkek. Having already been exposed to life away from home, different cultures, environments, and academic lifestyles, they found it easier to integrate compared to the others who arrived directly in the US without such prior experiences.

Some students struggle to connect with their Western classmates, finding it challenging to establish common ground for conversation. They often feel more at ease within the newly formed Afghan community at Bard College. Conversely, others have no difficulty befriending newly

arrived displaced students from Ukraine or students from India. They attribute this ease to a shared experience of displacement and cultural similarity.

One participant expressed difficulty in socializing with American classmates due to a lack of common ground, such as no familiarity with anything they follow like its singers, actresses, life, cities, and places. Social and cultural disparities between their host and native countries can impede international students' academic progress. Integrating with domestic students in the United States is crucial for some, but communication barriers, including language and cultural differences, make it challenging for them to connect with American peers (Darwish, 2022). Traditional differences were also identified as another challenging factor to adapt to. For instance, one participant noted, "Smoking and drinking are considered cool and fun, which poses a challenge compared to our tradition."

The interview also highlighted the complex dynamics of support and treatment of Afghan students within academic settings. It highlighted the nuanced challenges faced by students who may feel uncomfortable with preferential treatment based on their nationality, preferring fair and unbiased evaluation and the importance of providing constructive feedback to students to facilitate their academic growth and development. One participant described how their professor's reaction and grading changed upon learning they were from Afghanistan, leading to feelings of discomfort due to perceived pity. She said "Although I received an 'A' grade in one of my courses, I wasn't satisfied. I felt that the professor's pity due to fact that I am from an Afghan influenced the grade, rather than my actual performance. Despite receiving a high grade, the participant felt it was unjustified solely based on their nationality, highlighting concerns about fair grading practices and

a lack of detailed feedback compared to previous educational experiences. It suggests a need for greater awareness and sensitivity among educators towards the diverse backgrounds and experiences of their students, fostering an inclusive and supportive learning environment.

Culture Shock

According to Lipson and Meleis (1983) during migration, individuals or families often lose their social networks and essential resources, leading to feelings of disorganization and disorientation, known as cultural exhaustion or shock. Interpreting the behavior and symbols of others becomes challenging, requiring significant energy. Meeting basic needs like housing, food, navigating the banking system, and learning English demands considerable effort. Furthermore, immigrants may experience varying degrees of loss, from mild to profound.

“I find it disrespectful to see people on phone and it has been a day-to-day challenge for me and I have hard time making friends.” Said one participant. Students find it hard to accept culture of mobile phones or digital devices while having a normal conversation and it has a lot to do how they were raised and participants expressed how conversation with professors or faculty was nicer as they were not so involved with technologies while having a normal conversation.

International students face cultural adjustments upon arriving in the US, navigating unfamiliar customs and social norms. Challenges include relationships, gestures, and networking, leading to cultural shock. Afghan students, for example, may struggle with informal classroom dynamics. Transitioning from a collective to individualistic culture further complicates social interactions. Despite efforts to foster intercultural relations, genuine connections are hindered by language barriers and unfamiliar protocols. As a result, students often form closer bonds within

smaller, homogeneous groups (Darwish, 2022). While most participants experienced culture shock, those who had been through experience of living in countries like Iraq, Bishkek, and the US before coming to the US were more familiar with the transition, unlike those who came directly from Afghanistan. For example, one participant found the transition easy due to prior experience at AUIS in Kurdistan, where campus life resembled that at Bard. "Dating culture here is different, as people are not engaged too much, and everyone is too much into their phone screens. Trying to date is tough, especially with the young generation at Bard."

3. Economic challenges

Financial crises are another challenge that international students may encounter. Contrary to the assumption of their wealth, many international students' express concerns about insufficient funds. Limited opportunities for employment outside of school and federal financial aid exacerbate their financial difficulties, as immigration regulations impose strict constraints on non-U.S. residents (Darwish, 2022). Upon their arrival in the US, students faced their greatest challenge: the economic situation.

Many students arrived with minimal funds, sometimes just a few hundred dollars or even nothing at all, which made it difficult to cover expenses beyond basic necessities that only lasted them weeks. Although all students were provided with a meal plan and dormitory accommodation, they lacked any stipend or means of income. For example, one participant, who was part of the first cohort to arrive at Bard College on a fully funded scholarship from Qatar IIE (Institute for International Education), found that while the scholarship covered food expenses, there was no stipend provided. She expressed a desire for financial support and the opportunity to work off-campus upon her initial arrival.

Providing support

Providing opportunities for Afghan students to pursue graduate studies abroad, with the intention of returning home after graduation, not only strengthens higher education but also helps overcome suspicion and pessimism. Despite obstacles, educational partnership projects remain the best, if not the only, method to enhance the understanding of higher education administrators in Afghanistan, ultimately increasing their involvement and leadership, which are critical for success (Esmaily et al., 2010).

Bard College's significant support for Afghan students, particularly in legal and administrative matters. While the participant managed her asylum paperwork independently, Bard facilitated access to legal assistance, including pro-bono lawyers and informative sessions on the legal system which the student was grateful.

Educators with expertise in aiding Afghan refugees emphasize the significance of hiring personnel who possess cultural understanding and language proficiency as the primary method to help with Afghan refugee students (Deng, 2022). Participants highlighted, the cultural support was also provided by Bard college by organizing Afghan food events and making academic exceptions, such as add and drop dates. Additionally, various departments, including admissions, disability services, and student activities, played pivotal roles in accommodating students' needs and aiding. This comprehensive support system underscores Bard College's commitment to fostering a supportive environment for its diverse student body, particularly evident in legal aid provision and administrative support for Afghan students that help Afghan students succeed.

4. Psychological problems

To manage the psychological toll of enduring war, conflict, and the upheaval of evacuating amidst the collapse of the Afghan government, many students employ coping mechanisms. Some choose to disconnect from events in their homeland, while others seek solace through therapy sessions or maintain strong connections with family back home. Engaging with the Afghan community offers solidarity and understanding during these challenging times.

The challenges faced by Middle Eastern immigrants, particularly Afghan Americans, in adapting their cultural values, beliefs, and behaviors are highlighted in research by Wahidi (2015). Wahidi's study on depressive symptoms and acculturative stress among Afghan immigrants in the United States underscores the difficulties associated with cultural adaptation.

Many participants, whose asylum cases were pending when they arrived to the US, expressed concerns about their status in the country, which greatly hampers their ability to find employment and face travel restrictions, exacerbating their psychological problems. To mitigate these challenges, Bard College has offered counseling services to newly arrived Afghan students. Participants have emphasized the transformative impact of these therapy sessions on their daily lives at Bard College and in overcoming trauma.

The low use of counseling services among international students doesn't mean counseling doesn't work for them. It suggests a need to adapt counseling practices to better suit their cultural backgrounds (Mori, 2000). In addition to typical student developmental concerns, international

students face extra stressors related to cultural adjustments. These include challenges with language, academics, interpersonal relationships, finances, and personal issues, which contribute to their unique stress experiences (Mori, 2000, p.137). All these challenges are concerning that can lead to serious psychological problems. One participant said that "I don't need a certificate to get a job, and it is depressing being separated from my family; it damages a person," emphasizing the significance of belonging to one's community and being close to family.

Addressing Trauma old and new

Refugees who come to the United States frequently require extensive counseling to address both the traumas they have experienced in their past and the potential traumas that may arise during the resettlement process (Trauth & Harris). Immigrants arriving in the United States encounter emotional difficulties such as xenophobia, intolerance, and various significant challenges. These encounters can significantly impact mental well-being, leading to an increased risk of developing PTSD. For effective support of immigrants in the U.S., counselors and psychologists should offer culturally sensitive services like the multi-level model MLM model of Psychotherapy and multicultural social justice career programs. They must also advocate for this group by understanding their pre- and post-immigration experiences. Recommendations include moving beyond traditional counseling to holistic approaches that integrate social justice and human rights into therapy. (Chung, Bemak, and Grabosky, 2011).

Some students actively engage with their community by seeking on-campus employment, participating in therapy sessions offered by Bard College, and becoming more socially involved in campus events. Additionally, they consciously choose to avoid consuming news related to the

events unfolding in Afghanistan, which aids them in coping with the trauma resulting from the Taliban's recent takeover. To highlight this, one participant said that “Therapy has really helped me overcome a lot of my emotional and mental challenges in the United States”.

Extensive research on acculturation offers valuable insights for counselors and mental health professionals assisting immigrants. Berry in his 1997 research specifically examines the experiences of immigrants adjusting to a new culture after being uprooted from their original one. Berry's model delineates four potential outcomes for immigrants based on their unique circumstances. These outcomes, including assimilation, integration, separation, and marginalization, reflect the immigrant's adaptation to the host country's culture and their retention of their homeland's cultural identity. Understanding these outcomes is crucial for guiding counselors in supporting immigrants during the resettlement process (Berry, 2010 as cited in Trauth & Harris, pp. 28-29). Participants highlighted that attending in-person classes and being far from family, as well as feeling isolated from their home country, can be tiring and exhausting. One participant expressed, "I would prefer having my family around me and taking classes online; being by myself is the biggest challenge for me."

Conclusion

In conclusion, the literature review sheds light on vital aspects concerning Afghan students newly resettled in the US post-2021. It reveals the profound impact of enduring internal conflicts on Afghanistan's societal fabric and education landscape, contributing to gender disparities and driving migration due to economic instability and conflict. Moreover, it highlights the pivotal role of higher education in fostering global connections and cultural exchange, alongside the complex challenges faced by Afghan students in the US.

In this research paper, the goal was to shed light on the voices of Afghan students, urging universities and colleges in the United States to be mindful of the unique needs and challenges of international student including newly arrived Afghan students. By doing so, we can facilitate their smoother integration into the U.S. academic system. To answer my questions, through in-depth interviews, participants shared their struggles and triumphs, highlighting the resilience and determination that characterize their experiences. From grappling with cultural shock to navigating unfamiliar academic systems and financial constraints, each hurdle underscores the depth of their adaptation process.

Importantly, the findings underscore the critical role of tailored support services in facilitating the academic and personal success of Afghan students. These challenges include academic integration hurdles, economic constraints, and psychological stressors. It underscores the critical need for cultural orientation programs to mental health resources and financial aid, these services play a pivotal role in easing their transition and fostering a sense of belonging.

Ultimately, this research paper emphasized the vital importance of collaboration among educators, administrators, and mental health professionals in fostering an inclusive and nurturing atmosphere for Afghan students. Recognizing their individual struggles and offering tailored assistance, academic institutions can empower Afghan students to not just succeed but to also enrich their communities. The findings shed light on the resilience, bravery, and unwavering resolve of Afghan students after their arrival in 2021 as they navigate the difficult journey of resettlement, forging ahead towards their academic and personal goals.

Recommendation

Considering increasing student enrollment, students recommend Bard College to expand job opportunities, especially for those unable to secure on-campus employment due to restrictions. Efforts to facilitate off-campus job placements, particularly for displaced students, are essential. Bard should actively foster connections with potential employers, offer post-graduation job placement assistance, and strengthen ties with alumni networks. Furthermore, financial support initiatives, such as loans, and tailored assistance for displaced students in navigating opportunities beyond campus should be explored.

Moreover, students advocate for a structured period of academic exploration within Bard's liberal arts curriculum, allowing students to sample diverse courses before declaring a major. Enhanced academic support, particularly for students grappling with English proficiency and active participation in discussions, is crucial. Leveraging successful initiatives like Bard's Afghan-to-Afghan peer mentor program could serve as a blueprint for supporting incoming Afghan students, fostering community, and providing invaluable transitional support.

The asylum interview and processing procedures need enhancement for newly arrived Afghans to prevent prolonged backlogs that have persisted for years. Additionally, efforts should focus on expediting the resettlement process for students whose families remain stranded in Afghanistan.

Limitation

It is important to note that I only interviewed a limited number of seven participants, which may not fully reflect the perspectives of the broader Afghan population evacuated and who are studying in US colleges. Another limitation was the absence of earlier research on the resettlement of Afghan students post-2021 in the United States, integrating the findings with existing literature may be challenging. Getting people on "zoom" interviews were not as effective compared to in-person meetings that I had. Lastly, to streamline my study, I specifically focused on Afghan students evacuated or arriving on F1 visas post-2021, on full scholarships at Bard College, rather than including students from other institutions. This allowed me to narrow the scope and concentrate on a single state. Despite these limitations, the study offers valuable insights into the resettlement experiences of Afghan students in the United States. Since it is the first qualitative analysis of its kind, further research is needed to explore this phenomenon using different approaches and to compare findings.

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